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D5.3. Initial report on clustering and liaising with other initiatives

General information

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Glossary¹

Term	Description
Access	Access to the research infrastructures under the project AgroServ is provided free of charge to the User/User Groups once their proposals for the use of services have been approved and passed the eligibility criteria, and the feasibility and scientific evaluations during the selection phases. For more details see D1.3 AgroServ Access Policy.
Access Manager	Manager of access and service provision in a Research Infrastructure.
Access Provider	Manage of a specific facility or service within an organisation that is a member of a Research infrastructure.
AE	Agroecology
AgroServ	The present project providing integrated services to support the sustainable agroecological transition.
DMP	Data Management Plan: guidelines for management of data within AgroServ.
Facility or Installation	Facility or installation (used as synonyms) required for the implementation of a specific service, usually users obtain access to experimental providing specific services (experimentation, data analysis etc.).
LL	Living Lab
Proposal Review Committee	Panel of independent experts that will assess the Transnational Access applications.
RI	Facilities or installation that provide resources and services for the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. For more details see D1.3 AgroServ Access Policy.
TAVA	Trans-National and Virtual Access allowing third party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation's research facilities (installations) and services (TA) and access to an organisation's cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services such as data analysis/analysis pipeline set-up or other more "operational" components.
User or User Group	The external committer of resources that exploits the transnational or virtual access services offered by the AgroServ project; the user can be an individual or a team of researchers from the public or private sector.

¹ <https://agroserv.eu/calls-and-applications/glossary-technical-terms>

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WP	Work Package. A set of related activities within a project.
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Executive summary

This deliverable 5.3. “*Initial report on clustering and liaising with other initiatives*” aims at ensuring appropriate links and complementarities with existing research projects and initiatives relevant for achieving sustainable and resilient agriculture and agroecological transitions. To that end, we first discuss the concepts of synergies and highlight why they are of relevance for the Horizon Europe project, AgroServ. In sections 2 and 3, we highlight the specific objectives and methods followed to find those synergies. In section 4, we provide the mapping and categorization of the different projects, networks, platforms and associations relevant for clustering and liaising with them. Fifthly, we describe the action plan to link with relevant and complementary initiatives, including a centralized project strategy as well as individual-lead effort from AgroServ project partners. Lastly, we provided tools for monitoring the collaboration and synergistic actions performed by AgroServ consortium partners.

This deliverable is framed under *Task 5.2. Clustering and liaising with other relevant initiatives and projects* of WP5 *Community building and users’ engagement*. This is the first of a series of three reports that will describe the process of clustering and liaising with relevant EU related initiatives. The reports will be updated at least at M36 and M60.

1. The concept of synergies

Synergy is the *combined power of a group of things when they are working together that is greater than the total power achieved by each working separately*. By developing synergies, we aim to maximize the added value and impact of current or past projects, platforms, networks, associations, and other initiatives by identifying resources, leveraging these resources and creating new sources of value that form the base for building synergy.

Synergies and collaborations between projects and initiatives can generate a wide range of opportunities.

They can help to **capitalize lessons learned** from one project that are applied to future projects, leading to improved performance over time and prevents repeating the same errors. It can also prevent overlapping of actions and allowing to create greater efficiency, fosters innovation and improve the scope of the results.

Synergies between projects can also lead to the **development of new and innovative solutions**. By bringing together diverse perspectives and interdisciplinary expertise, consortium members can find new opportunities and approaches that may not have been apparent before. Besides, leveraging synergies between projects can also help organizations to manage risks more effectively.

Synergies allow for **resource optimization** by coordinating efforts and sharing resources, such as expertise, facilities, and funding, synergistic projects can optimize resource utilization. This reduces duplication of efforts and maximizes the efficiency of research activities.

Synergies also **increase impact and visibility** by gathering greater and larger attention and recognition within the scientific community and beyond. By leveraging the combined expertise and resources of multiple partners, synergistic projects can achieve greater impact and visibility, leading to broader dissemination of research outcomes and increased opportunities for further collaboration and funding.

Synergies in research projects also **align with and increase the contribution to EU priorities**, such as the European Green Deal, Horizon Europe objectives, and other strategic initiatives. By addressing pressing societal challenges and advancing EU policy objectives, collaboration among projects can enhance the relevance and impact of EU-funded research efforts.

Lastly, and importantly, synergies **facilitate the exchange and dissemination of knowledge** and findings among researchers, policy makers, industry, and the general public. This enhances the impact of research outcomes by ensuring that valuable insights reach relevant stakeholders and are translated into tangible applications and policies.

In AgroServ, we foresaw two main types of synergies:

- **Static synergy** – the synergy effect results from the relationship between the project and existing outcomes generated by past projects, networks and initiatives. The synergies could be considered static since it is not possible to interact directly with the project activities or, at best, with the partners or project coordinator. Instead, their results will be possibly used for passively learning and exploiting their results. Thus, the information offered by past project outcomes will contribute to a sustainable use of resources under a synergistic process.

- **Dynamic synergies** – the synergy effect results from the relationship between likewise ongoing initiatives which are developing resources under a collaborative dimension. In this case, synergistic processes must be planned. Ongoing projects can create synergies based on adequate and synchronized roadmaps created for two or more projects. Relations with ongoing relevant platforms, networks, associations and enterprises were considered dynamic synergies.

2. Objectives

This report describes potential connections and collaborations that could be developed between the AgroServ consortium members and other related initiatives. Partnerships are foreseen not only with current or previous similar projects or related initiatives but also with associations, networks and enterprises. The synergies are expected to help the AgroServ consortium in learning from other projects' findings, upscaling the project's results, broadening project audience and improving the dissemination and use of results mainly within the Agroecology (AE) community in EU.

The aim of this report is therefore to establish deep ties with relevant platforms, networks, associations, and other related projects that could help obtain more robust results and greater impact on AE transitions and sustainable agriculture. Synergies with similar EU-funded projects will be exploited to increase the outreach of potential stakeholders, organize joint events, exchange knowledge, experience, and best practices, and stimulate discussions among key players. AgroServ will also build on its partners networks and platforms to boost these synergies and collaborations.

3. Methodological approach

This deliverable aims to be a living document, used to guide liaising actions conducted by the AgroServ consortium.

Firstly, during the first year of the project, we started identifying the different projects, networks, platforms and associations relevant to the project. A preliminary database was created with the support of all partners of the consortium. Detailed information of each initiative considered of relevance for AgroServ partners was included in the database. The database was thereafter complemented and cleaned-up through a grey literature review, including relevant EU projects identified on CORDIS Database². This database is a living document in constant revision by consortium members.

For each initiative, we gathered general basic information (i.e. acronym, name, type, web, contact details) as well as information on duration, keywords and objectives of the initiative. This information was complemented by adding the identification of potential synergies (by categorization), a prioritization based on stated consortium importance (Tables 1, 2, 3 and 4) and barriers for collaboration (if any).

Secondly, we generated an action plan to liaise with other initiatives in which two different types of approaches were identified: i) a centralized liaison strategy coordinated by the leaders of WP5

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/>

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(Stakeholders engagement), WP8 (Communication) and WP9 (Project coordination) leaders and ii) a liaison strategy led by each project partner with the support of the centralized liaison approach team. While the objective of the first is to boost synergies and collaborations of interest for the project as a whole, the second aims to focus on initiatives of thematic or geographical relevant and interest for each specific Research Infrastructure (RI), groups of RIs and consortium members. A dedicated communication kit has been developed by the AgroServ communication officer to support AgroServ partners in their liaison with other initiatives strategy.

Finally, to track the different actions performed by each AgroServ partners, promote coordination among the different liaison activities and prevent stakeholders' fatigue, a template has been developed (Annex 1) with basic information to be completed after each interaction.

4. Identification of projects, networks, platforms and associations

Following the process mentioned in Section 3, a list of initiatives for which **static synergies** have been identified by consortium members is listed in Table 1. The main initiatives that the project as a whole has liaised with are: *Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU)*, *The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase (ALL-Ready)* and *Towards a new EU-LAC partnership in Research Infrastructures (ResInfra EU-LAC)*.

AE4EU and ALL-Ready are Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs), funded under Horizon 2020, to strengthen the European agroecological research and innovation ecosystem by developing a framework for a European network of agroecological living labs (LL) and research infrastructures. These two project set up the basis for the preparation of the Co-funded EU Partnership on accelerating farming systems transition – agroecology living labs and research infrastructures. Collaboration has been already established among those 2 projects and material (e.g. LLs mapping, experience on the VRE) from ALL-Ready and AE4EU has been shared with AgroServ consortium. Additionally, AgroServ was present through the participation of AnaEE-ERIC and LifeWatch ERIC in different panels of the the final joint conference that took place 27 September 2023, in which the experience on how AgroServ could support AE transition from a theoretical and practical perspective was given (Figure 1).

Final agenda - Afternoon session

- 13:45-14:45 Panel: How can Living Labs and Research Infrastructures support the agroecology transition? Q&A
Martina Desole, European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL)
Jan Hassink, Wageningen Research
Chris McPhee, Living Laboratories Division, Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC)
Lavanya Premvardhan, European Research Infrastructure Consortium on Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems (AnaEE-ERIC)
Paola Migliorini, University of Gastronomic Sciences (UNISG) Polenzo (moderator)
- 14:45-16:15 Practice perspectives: How to put agroecology Living Labs and Research Infrastructures in practice? Q&A
Véronique Bellon-Maurel, Occitanium Living Lab (France)
Judith Conroy, Coventry University (United Kingdom)
Lieve De Cock, Living Lab Agroecology and Organic Agriculture (LLAEBIO) (Flanders)
Bregje Hamelynck, Federation of Agroecological Farmers (Netherlands)
Giuliana Radosta, Agroecological Living Lab Val Varaita (Italy)
Iria Soto, E-Science European Infrastructure For Biodiversity And Ecosystem Research (LifeWatch-ERIC) (Spain)
Sylvie Foselle, Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO) (moderator)

Figure 1. Agenda of the final conference of All-Ready and AE4EU project with the two sessions in which AgroServ consortium was active (highlighted in yellow).

Table 1 – List of the 13 initiatives for static synergies (past initiatives but of interest for AgroServ consortium partners)

INITIATIVE ACRONYM	INITIATIVE NAME	INITIATIVE TYPE		DURATION	WEB	COORDINATOR ENTITY	PRIORITY	WPS
AE4EU	Agroecology for Europe	EU Project	H2020	Jan 21 - Dec23	https://www.ae4eu.eu/	ISARA	1	WP5; WP6
AllReady	The European Agroecology Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: Preparation phase	EU Project	H2020	Nov 20 - Oct 2023	https://www.all-ready-project.eu/	INRAE	1	WP5; WP6
ResInfra EU-LAC	Towards a new EU-LAC partnership in Research Infrastructures	EU Project	H2020	Dec 19- Oct 23	https://resinfra-eulac.eu/	Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (MICINN) Spain	1	WP8
AgriSafetyNet	aims to raise awareness and train farmers and agricultural authorities on health and safety education in agriculture.	EU Project	Erasmus	Sept 19 - Sept 21	http://www.agrisafetynet.eu/?lang=en	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra	2	WP8
AGROSMARTglobal	AGROSMARTglobal - Space of integration, competitiveness and intelligent economic growth of the agro-food cooperatives of the rural space SUDOE	EU Project	Interreg	Sep 19 - Jul 23	https://www.agrosmartglobal.eu/	Unión de Cooperativas Asociación Galega de Cooperativas Agrarias	2	WP8
BioBlitz	BioBlitz - promote and improve local natural spaces by empowering citizens to better understand and protect biodiversity	Project	Regional (BE)	nd	https://www.bioblitz.be/index.html	natuurpunt	2	WP8
CiDéSol	CiDéSol	Project	Regional (BE)	20-23	https://www.cocreate.brussels/projet/cidesol/	Laboratoire d'écologie végétale ULB	2	WP8
INTEGRURAL	Capacity Building for Integrated Sustainable Development in Rural Areas	EU Project	H2020	Sep 20 - Aug 23	https://www.integrural.eu/	CTRAD/UTAD	2	WP8
LEARNVIL	Learning Villages: Citizenship, Entrepreneurship, Heritage & Environmental Education for Rural Sustainable Development	EU Project	H2020	Mar 21 - Feb 23	https://www.learnville.eu/	SEPLE	2	WP8
LEGVALUE	Legume Innovation Network	EU Project	H2020	June 17 - May 21	https://www.legvalue.eu/	Processors & growers research organisation	2	WP8
MykoKey	Integrated and innovative key actions for mycotoxin management in the food and feed chain	EU Project	H2020	Apr 16 - Mar 20	http://www.mycokokey.eu/	CNR ISPA	2	WP5
SmartAKIS	Smart Farming Thematic network	EU Project	H2020	no data available	https://www.smart-akis.com/	Iniciativas innovadoras	2	WP8
Stargate	Stargate	EU Project	H2020	Oct 19 -Sept 23.	https://www.stargate-h2020.eu/	CERTH	2	WP8
SUPER-G	Sustainable Permanent Grassland	EU Project	H2020	Jan 18 – Dec 20	https://www.super-g.eu/	Adas UK	2	WP2; WP5
LIVINGAGRO	Cross-border living labs for Agroforestry	EU Project	ENCBCMED	19-23	https://livingagrolab.eu/ (to be active soon)		2	WP6, WP8

Another relevant initiative is ResInfra EU-LAC³ project (finalized project but with a continuation called ResInfra Plus) which aims to: i) identify the characteristics that would facilitate the sharing of research infrastructures on an international level for making them open and available for researchers and ii) develop a coordinated work strategy among RIs. AgroServ could contribute by supporting them in the development of a sustainable framework for enhancing the regional collaboration of RIs between European Union and Latin America and the Caribbean. An exchange on RIs management and best practices of RIs collaboration has been identified as a synergy with them.

Figure 2. ResInfra EU-LAC meeting where synergies with AgroServ projects were identified (Madrid, 28 February, 2023) by the participation of LifeWatch ERIC.

Complementary to past initiatives, **dynamic synergies** with ongoing initiatives, projects, networks and platforms of relevance for AgroServ have also been mapped and identified by consortium partners and complemented by CORDIS database and internet search (Table 2).

Ongoing **farmers groups, associations and NGOs** of relevance for AgroServ have also been mapped by consortium partners (Table 3) and synergies with them will be established with two main objectives: i) identify the research needs of these end-user groups and ii) disseminate the results of the project.

Companies, mainly SME of relevance for AgroServ partners have also been identified (Table 4). Specific communication actions will be performed to encourage their participation, in partnership with farmers associations and research centres, in the coming AgroServ call for proposals foreseen for next year.

The most relevant identified initiatives for potential dynamic synergies with AgroServ consortium are also publicly available in a dedicated section of the webpage of the AgroServ project (<https://agroserv.eu/outreach-and-impact/knowledge-transfer>). The page will be updated periodically.

³ EU-LAC (European Union - Latin America and the Caribbean)

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All identified initiatives, projects, networks, platforms, associations and NGOs of relevance for AgroServ will be invited to be part of the AgroServ Community of Users (T5.1).

Table 2 – List of the of identified initiatives for potential dynamic synergies with AgroServ consortium (summarized information)

n	INITIATIVE ACRONYM	INITIATIVE NAME	INITIATIVE TYPE	WEB	PRIORITY	WPs
1	Agroecology partnership	Agroecology partnership	EU partnership	not yet available	1	WP5, WP8, WP9
2	FutureFoodS	European Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems	EU partnership	https://scar-europe.org/index.php/food/food-main-actions/food-systems-partnership	1	WP5, WP8, WP9
3	PRIMA	Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area (PRIMA) Joint Programme	EU Partnership	https://prima-med.org/	1	WP6, WP7, WP8
4	Agromix	Agromix	EU Project	https://agromixproject.eu/	2	WP5, WP8
5	Agroecology transect	Trans-disciplinary approaches for Systemic economic, Ecological and Climate change Transitions	EU Project	https://www.agroecology-transect.net/	1	WP2, WP5, WP8
6	Bicikl	Biodiversity Community Integrated Knowledge Library	EU Project	https://bicikl-project.eu/	1	WP1,WP2
7	CANSERV	Providing Cutting-Edge Cancer Research Services Across Europe	EU Project	https://www.canserv.eu/	1	WP1,WP2
8	EOSC-Life	Building a digital space for Life Sciences	EU Project	https://www.eosc-life.eu/	1	WP1, WP3, WP8, WP9
9	EU-LAC RESINFRA PLUS	Advance bi-regional #research infrastructures and maintain sustainable collaboration at the governmental level.	EU Project	not yet available	1	WP3; WP5; WP7, WP9
10	IRISCC	IRISCC – Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks	EU Project	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131261	1	WP2; WP3, WP5; WP7
11	Isidore	Integrated services for infectious disease outbreak research	EU Project	https://isidore-project.eu/	1	WP1,WP2
12	MARINNET	Transnational R&D&I cooperation network to foster the competitiveness and sustainability of the Blue Biotech sector in the Atlantic Area territory.	EU Project	not yet available	1	WP2, WP5, WP8
13	M4C	Microbes for Climate	EU Project	Not yet available	1	WP1, WP5, WP9
14	PHENET	Tools and methods for extended plant PHENotyping and EnviroTyping services of European Research Infrastructures	EU Project	https://www.phenet.eu/en	1	WP1, WP5, WP9
15	SoildiverAgro	SoildiverAgro	EU Project	http://soildiveragro.eu/	1	WP5; WP8
16	SOLO	Soils for Europe	EU Project	https://soils4europe.eu/	1	WP2, WP5, WP8, WP9
17	VITALISE	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure	EU project	https://vitalise-project.eu/	1	WP1, WP3, WP5, WP6

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n	INITIATIVE ACRONYM	INITIATIVE NAME	INITIATIVE TYPE	WEB	PRIORITY	WPs
18	FAO	The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations	International organization	https://www.fao.org/	1	WP2, WP8
19	FACCE-JPI	Joint Programming Initiative on Agriculture, Food Security and Climate Change	Network	https://www.faccejpi.net/	1	WP2, WP7, WP8
20	JRC- Agroecology	Joint Research Centre – Agroecology	Research group	https://commission.europa.eu/about-european-commission/departments-and-executive-agencies/joint-research-centre_en	1	WP5, WP8, WP9
21	MERIL	Mapping the European Research Infrastructure Landscape	database (project-H2020)	https://portal.meril.eu/meril/static/static_mac	2	WP9
22	Biodiversa+	The European Biodiversity Partnership	EU Partnership	https://www.biodiversa.eu/	2	WP3, WP7, WP8
23	EJP Soil	European Joint Programming SOIL	EU Partnership	https://ejpsoil.eu/	2	WP3, WP6, WP8
24	Knowledge Centre for Global Food and Nutrition Security	Knowledge Centre for Global Food and Nutrition Security	EU platform	https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/global-food-nutrition-security/topic/agroecology_en	2	WP8
25	AquaServ	Service for aquaculture, fisheries and blue economy	EU Project	Not yet available	2	WP1, WP5, WP9
26	BENCHMARKS	Creating a soil health monitoring framework for Europe	EU Project	https://soilhealthbenchmarks.eu/	2	WP8
27	COCOREADO	Conecting consumers and producers to rebalance farmers' position	EU Project	https://cocoreado.eu/	2	WP5, WP8,
28	CROPINNO	Stepping up scientific excellence and innovation capacity for climate-resilient crop improvement and production	EU Project	https://cropinno.org/	2	WP1, WP8
29	ECHO	Engaging Citizens in soil science: the road to Healthier sOils	EU Project	https://echosoil.eu/	2	WP8
30	EU-LAC RESINFRA PLUS	Towards A Sustainable EU-LAC Partnership In Research Infrastructures	EU Project	https://resinfra-eulac.eu/	2	WP3, WP5, WP7
31	FoddSafety4EU	FoodSafety4EU - Multi-stakeholder platform for food safety in Europe	EU Project	https://foodsafety4.eu/	2	WP2, WP2, WP5, WP7, WP9
32	Francisco Chaves CETRAD	LivingSoiLL	EU Project	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-miss-2023-soil-01-08	2	WP6, WP8, WP9
33	IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks	EU Project	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131261	2	WP1, WP5, WP9
34	MARVIC	Monitoring, Reporting & Verification (MRV) systems for carbon farming	EU Project	https://www.project-marvic.eu/	2	WP8

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n	INITIATIVE ACRONYM	INITIATIVE NAME	INITIATIVE TYPE	WEB	PRIORITY	WPs
35	Mixed	Multi-actor and transdisciplinary development of efficient and resilient MIXED farming and agroforestry systems	EU Project	https://projects.au.dk/mixed/	2	WP2, WP8, WP9
36	Natae	Fostering agroecology transition in North Africa through multi-actor, evaluation, and networking	EU Project	https://www.natae-agroecology.eu/	2	WP2, WP8
37	NBSOILS	Nature Based Solutions for Soil Management	EU Project	https://nbsoil.eu/	2	WP8
38	NOVASOIL	Innovative Business models for soil health	EU Project	https://novasoil-project.eu/	2	WP8
39	Organictargets4eu	Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets	EU Project	https://www.organictargets.eu/	2	WP5, WP8, WP9
40	PREPSOIL	Preparing for the 'Soil Deal for Europe' Mission	EU Project	https://prepsoil.eu/	2	WP8
41	Soil-Olive	Soil Biodiversity and functionality of Mediterranean Olive grooves	EU Project	https://soilolive.eu/	2	WP2, WP8
42	ENI CBC Med	Cooperation in the mediterranean	funding programme	https://www.enicbcmed.eu/home	2	WP7, WP9
43	BIOEAST	Central And Eastern European Initiative for Knowledge-Based Agriculture, Aquaculture And Forestry In The Bioeconomy	Network	https://bioeast.eu/	2	WP7, WP8
44	EIP- AGRI	EU CAP Network (EIP- AGRI)	network	https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/about-european-cap-network_en	2	WP5; WP8
45	ENAF	European Network for Agroecological Food systems	network	https://www.ae4eu.eu/enaf-european-network-of-agroecological-food-systems-the-story-continues/	2	WP8
46	IPPN	International Plant Phenotyping Network	network	https://www.plant-phenotyping.org/	2	WP8, WP9
47	JPI AMR	Joint Programming Initiative on Antimicrobial Resistance	Network	https://www.jpiamr.eu/	2	WP2, WP7, WP8
48	IPES-Food	International Panel of Experts on Sustainable Food Systems	Panel of expert	https://ipes-food.org/	2	WP8, WP9
49	TP organics	European Technology Platform (for organic food & farming)	platform	https://tporganics.eu/	2	WP8
50	D4AgEcol	Digitalisation for Agroecology	EU Project	https://d4agecol.eu/	3	WP8
51	DigitAf	DIGItal Tools to boost AgroForestry	EU Project	https://digitaf.eu/	3	WP8
52	EcoStack	Stacking of ecosystem services: mechanisms & interactions for optimal crop protection, pollination enhancement and productivity	EU Project	https://www.ecostack-h2020.eu/	3	WP8

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n	INITIATIVE ACRONYM	INITIATIVE NAME	INITIATIVE TYPE	WEB	PRIORITY	WPs
53	Grazing 4 Agroecology	European Network to promote grazing and to support grazing-based farms on their economic and ecologic performances as well as on animal welfare	EU Project	https://grazing4agroecology.eu/	3	WP8
54	GREAT	Green Deal Data Space	EU project	https://www.greatproject.eu/great-project-consortium/	3	WP3
55	InnoBreed	Innovative Organic Fruit Breeding and uses	EU Project	https://innobreed.eu/	3	WP8
56	LiveSeeding	Organic seed and plant breeding to accelerate sustainable and diverse food systems in Europe	EU Project	https://www.liveseed.eu/	3	WP8
57	LivingSoiLL	LivingSoiLL - Co-creating solutions for soil health in Living Labs	EU Project	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-miss-2023-soil-01-08	3	WP2, WP5, WP6
58	Path2Dea	Paving the Way towards Digitalisation Enabling Agroecology for European Farming Systems	EU Project	https://www.path2dea.eu/index.html	3	WP8
59	Reforest	Agroforestry at the forefront of farming sustainability in multifunctional landscapes in Europe.	EU Project	https://agroreforest.eu/	3	WP2, WP5, WP8
60	Urbane	One Health Approaches to support the AE transformation of peri-urban farming	EU Project	https://urbane-project.eu/	3	WP8
61	FoReSTAS	FoReSTAS	governmental forestry agency	https://www.sardegnaforeste.it/	3	WP8
62	Agroecology coalition	Agroecology coalition	Network	https://agroecology-coalition.org/	3	W8
63	The Finnish Rural Network	The Finnish Rural Network	Network	https://maaseutuverkosto.fi/en/	3	WP8
64	Plants for the future	European Technology Platform	Platform	https://www.plantetp.eu/	3	WP8
65	Chambres d'agriculture	Chambres d'agriculture francaises	Public entity	https://chambres-agriculture.fr/	3	WP8,WP9
66	InsacAGRIS	Integrated system for automated control of experimental agricultural land, by air/ground remote control transmission for precision agriculture	Regional project	https://insac-agris.eu/	3	WP8
67	WSP	« Wallonie sans pesticides »- Nature & Progrès	Regional project	natpro.be	3	WP5, WP8
68	FAMOSOS	FAMOSOS - Managing and mapping agricultural soils for enhancing soil functions and services	Regional project (PT)	https://ejpsoil.eu/soil-research/second-external-call-international-call	3	WP5
69	Vine & Wine	Vine & Wine - Driving Sustainable Growth Through Smart Innovation	Regional project (PT)	https://www.citab.utad.pt/index.php/projects/793/show	3	WP5, WP8
70	SCAR-AE	SCAR Strategic Working Group on Agroecology (SCAR-AE)	Working group	https://scar-europe.org/index.php/agroecology	3	WP8

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Table 3 – List of ongoing farmers groups, associations and NGOs of relevance for clustering with AgroServ

INITIATIVE ACRONYM	INITIATIVE NAME	INITIATIVE TYPE	WEB	PRIORITY	SYNERGIES
AEEU	Agroecology Europe Association	Association	https://www.agroecology-europe.org/	1	WP5, WP8
Agrihubl	Agrihubl	Association	https://maaseutuverkosto.fi/en/agrihubi/	1	WP8
BSAG	Baltic Sea Action Group	Association	https://www.bsag.fi/sv/kontakt/anne-antman/	1	WP8
CopaCogeca	European Farmers and European Agri-Cooperatives	Association	https://copa-cogeca.eu/	1	WP5, WP8
ELO	European Farmers Association	Association	https://europeanlandowners.org/	1	WP5, WP8
IFOAM	IFOAM Organics Europe	Association	https://www.ifoam.bio/	1	WP5, WP8
BCTI	BCTI international technical cooperation bureau	Association	https://www.bcti.online/en/	2	WP5, WP8
Coldiretti	Confederazione Nazionale	Association	https://www.coldiretti.it/	2	WP8
CEJA	European Council of young farmers	Association	https://www.ceja.eu/home	2	WP5, WP8
EPSO	European Plant Science Organisation	Association	https://epsoweb.org/	2	WP8
EAAP	European Association of Animal Science	Association	https://www.eaap.org/	2	WP8
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners	Association	https://www.mtk.fi/web/en	2	WP8
OPTA	Organic processing and trade association	Association	https://opta-eu.org/	2	WP6, WP8
Blconsortium	Biobased Industry Consortium	NGO	https://biconsortium.eu	2	WP8
BioRomania	Association of Organic Agriculture Operators	NGO	https://asociatia.bio/	2	WP5, WP8
EATIP	European Aquaculture Technology and Innovation action	NGO	https://eatip.eu/about/	2	WP8
ATF	Animal Task Force	NGO	https://animaltaskforce.eu/	2	WP8
I am more than my receipt	I am more than my receipt	NGO	https://www.rikolto.org/projects/i-am-more-than-my-receipt	2	WP8
InfoCons	The InfoCons Association	NGO	https://infocons.ro/	2	WP8
AgriCord	AgriCord	Association	https://www.agricord.org/en	3	WP8
ASRO	Association for Standardization in Romania	NGO	https://www.asro.ro/	3	WP4, WP5, WP7, WP8

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ProAgria	ProAgria	Association	https://www.proagria.fi/en	3	WP8
CREA	fair and sustainable products from Ecuador for the European market	NGO	https://www.rikolto.org/projects/crea-fair-and-sustainable-products-from-ecuador-for-the-european-market	3	WP8

Table 4 – List of companies for potential clustering with AgroServ

INITIATIVE NAME	INITIATIVE TYPE	WEB	PRIORITY	SYNERGIES
AGROECO_RESTORE	SME	inspirared.ecuador@gmail.com	3	WP8
Agrofood-BIC	SME	http://www.agrofoodbic.it/	3	WP8
Apheabio	SME	https://aphea.bio/	3	WP8
Bioazul	SME	https://www.bioazul.com/en/	3	WP8
Dale Farm Ltd	SME	https://dalefarm.com/our-story	3	WP8
ELOI	SME	https://eloi.eu/	3	WP8
Graham's Family Dairy	SME	https://www.grahamsfamilydairy.com/our-story/	3	WP8
Honkajoki Ltd	SME	https://honkajokioy.fi/en/	3	WP8
Soilfood Ltd	SME	https://soilfood.fi/en/	3	WP8
The polish farm advisory and training centre	SME	https://www.farm-advisory.eu/en/	3	WP8
Vallefiorita	SME	https://www.vallefiorita.it/	3	WP8
Yeo Valley Organic Limited	SME	https://www.yeovalley.co.uk/	3	WP8
AGROECO_RESTORE	SME	inspirared.ecuador@gmail.com	3	WP8
VARTLAB	SME	https://leap4fnssa.eu/agora_vartlab/	3	WP8
Greensolutions	SME	https://greensolutionsmaroc.com/	3	WP8

5. Liaising strategy action plan

A liaising strategy plan has been developed, which aims at ensuring appropriate links and complementarities with existing research projects and initiatives relevant for achieving sustainable and resilient agriculture and agroecological transitions.

Two different types of implementation approaches will be foreseen to maximize the capacity to liaise with other initiatives (Figure 3). A **centralized liaison strategy** and a **liaison strategy led by each project partner** with the support of the centralized liaison team.

LIASING STRATEGY & ROLE

Figure 3. Scheme of the AgroServ liaison strategy under the two approaches.

As a first common step for both approaches, a **mapping of the most relevant initiatives**, research projects, networks, platforms, associations of interest to liaise with (Tables 2, 3 and 4) was performed by AgroServ project partners within WP5. Based on this information, a project database with general information of each initiative was generated and complemented with the identification of potential synergies. The categories selected for identifying synergies were the following ones.

Main categories agreed for the identification of synergies and collaboration with relevant initiatives

1. Service provision and TNA calls preparations (*WP1 related*)
2. Best practices on Interdisciplinary/transdisciplinary/multidisciplinary approaches (*WP2 related*)
3. Data Management Practices, Open and FAIR Data approaches (*WP3 related*)
4. Quality & Ethics procedure (*WP4 related*)
5. Co-creation and stakeholders' engagement successful approaches (*WP5 related*)
6. Training programmes in General and in Agroecology in particular (*WP5 related*)
7. Development and implementation of Living Labs – real needs & practical research (*WP6 related*)
8. Development of long-term collaboration strategies to ensure project sustainability (*WP7 related*)
9. Communication, dissemination and outreach purposes (*WP8 related*)
10. Management and Valorisation of RIs and the provision of their services (*WP9 related*)
11. Thematic collaborations based on sectors of the Agroecological Systems:
 - a. Aquaculture, fisheries
 - b. Livestock
 - c. Forestry
 - d. Agriculture
 - e. Soil (specially initiatives participating on the Soil Mission)

Additionally, a dedicated **communication kit** has also been developed by the AgroServ communication officer to support AgroServ partners in their liaison with other initiatives strategy. The communication material includes i) a PowerPoint presentation giving a general overview of “what we are and what we do”, ii) a digital brochure with more details on the project activities and their members and iii) an email template to facilitate contacting external stakeholders. Targeted videos and social network material would also be of use for identifying and establishing synergies. All information is available on the project Nextcloud under the “templates and communication kit” folder in WP8.

The **centralized liaison strategy** will focus on strategic initiatives of interest and that will bring value for the whole project. This strategy will increase the performance of research and innovation (R&I), capitalize existing knowledge and build sustainable long-term knowledge capacities and improve the overall impact of the R&I activities. The core liaison team is formed by WP5, WP8, WP9 leaders and, depending on the collaboration categories, identify for each initiative, the associated WP leader will also be engaged.

By the end of 2024, collaborations with at least the 20 initiatives of Table 5 as fundamental and priority will be established by the AgroServ consortium. Below we provide a summary of the synergies with initiatives as part of the centralized liaison strategy. This information will be completed in the next version of the deliverable.

Table 5. List of priority initiatives to be contacted during 2024

N	Project name	Synergy
1	Agroecology	EU partnership reference in Agroecology. Synergies are foreseen with all WPs but specifically with WP7- Expanding the capacities of RIs & LLs.
2	FutureFoods	Reference EU Partnership for a sustainable Future of Food Systems, relevant to liaise with food chain actors
3	PRIMA	EU partnership reference in farming systems and value chain in the Mediterranean, relevant to network with food chain actors
4	Agromix	Reference Agroecology Project applying transdisciplinary approach to assess resilience of Agroecology and mixed farming systems
5	Agroecology Transect	Reference project on nature-friendly farming practices, relevant to learn from the development of Innovation Hubs and their user-centre and transdisciplinarity approaches
6	Bicikl	Reference project in the provision of services processes and TNA call for applications
7	CanServ	Reference project in the provision of services processes and TNA call for applications
8	OSCARS	Reference project bringing together RIs for creating collaboration spaces. Key for integrating the catalogue of services and follow FAIR data principles.
9	EU-LAC RESINFRA +	Initiative engaging LAC RIs, relevant to expand AgroServ activities to non-EU regions
10	Integrated RIs Services 4 Climate Change Risks	INFRA Serv Project requiring, as AgroServ, the provision of integrated services to improve Europe's resilience to climate change
11	Isidore	Reference project in the provision of services processes and TNA call for applications
12	MARINNONET	Reference INFRA Serv project requiring, as AgroServ, the collaboration of transnational R&D&I cooperation network on sustainable aquaculture
13	Microbes4Climate	INFRA Serv Project requiring, as AgroServ, the provision of integrated services for the sustainable management of natural resources
14	Phenet	Reference project in the provision of services processes and TNA call for applications
15	SoilDiverAgro	Reference soil mission project, relevant for learning from the development of protocols for assessing and evaluate biodiversity
16	SOLO	Reference soil mission project, relevant to exchange the multidisciplinary approaches used for creating soil knowledge hub
17	Vitalise	EU Project with experience providing transnational and virtual access, experience on harmonization procedures regarding data management and LLs implementation
18	FAO	Key institution reference on Agroecology that could support in mainstreaming the promotion of our services and exchange information
19	FACCE-JPI	Programme to promote the integration and alignment of research resources, structures and services.
20	JRC Agroecology	Research & Policy interface working on Agroecology, relevant to bridge AgroServ results with policy needs and policy recommendations

The **AGROECOLOGY Partnership - Accelerating farming systems transition: Agroecology living labs and research infrastructures** is a key initiative, reference in European Agroecology with which we have identified many synergies that should be developed. For that reason, the majority of AgroServ efforts on synergies generation are currently being given in establishing collaborations with that consortium and specifically with WP7- Expanding the capacities of RIs & LLs.

AGROECOLOGY is an ambitious, large-scale European research and innovation partnership between the EC and 26 Member States and Associated Countries. It brings together 70 EU institutions with the objective of main-streaming the principles of AE, redesign EU farming systems and build-up collaborations to co-create and share knowledge and solutions to engage in AE transitions. In this partnership RIs play a key role through their contribution to making scientific knowledge on AE available for this transition. Additionally, this partnership is also connected with relevant initiatives

such as EJP SOIL, FACCE JPI and past ERA-NETs working in the field of sustainable agriculture and AE (i.e. FACCE SURPLUS, SusCrop, SusAN, C-IPM, Core Organics).

The AgroServ project has participated in different meetings with the coordinators and WP leaders of the Partnership. Additionally, AgroServ was represented in the Kick-off Meeting (Figure 4) in a dedicated roundtable session entitled “Landscape of other initiatives and developing synergies” in which other relevant initiatives such as FutureFoodS Partnership, EU Missions-Soil Deal for Europe and Water4All Partnership participated.

Figure 4. Agroecology Partnership kick-off meeting – February 28-29 (2024) with the representation of different AgroServ consortium members.

Since the beginning of AgroServ project, synergies have also been implemented with projects experienced in providing integrated services in the framework of TAVA. Exchanges with Horizon EU projects such as **CanServ**, **Bicikl**, **Isidore** and **Phenet** have been held to capitalize on their experience in the preparation, implementation and evaluation of TAVA calls for proposals to exchange about the features of the online catalogue of services or the evaluation procedures.

Phenet project was also invited to participate at the European Research Services on Agroecology Conference #ERSAC2023 organized by AgroServ in Prague (5-6 June 2023). They presented the experiences gained providing integrated RIs services and in the preparation process of TAVA calls for services.

Synergies with the Horizon 2020 European Project **Vitalise** have also been explored. This project’s main goal is to provide open access to Health and Wellbeing infrastructures. AgroServ consortium can benefit from their experience providing transnational and virtual access for performing research activities. Additionally, their experience on harmonization procedures regarding data management procedures and LLs implementation are also of interest for AgroServ. Follow-up conversations with WP3, WP6 leaders are foreseen.

AgroServ also participated in the **Soil Mission Week** held in Madrid in October 2023. During that week, we got the chance to liaise with EU policymakers such as Kerstin Rosenow (Head of Unit Research and Innovation) or Piotr Wojda and Cristina Arias-Navarro (Scientific Research Officers

from the JRC). We learned the specificities of the Soil Mission strategy and actions and exchanged and networked with representatives of different Soil Mission Projects such as NBSOILS, NOVASOIL; PREPSOIL, MARVIC, BENCHMARKS, Soil-Olive or ECHO, among others (Table 5).

We are currently exploring synergies with other EU projects with the implementation of transdisciplinarity actions in AE research i.e. **AgroMix**, **Transect**, **SOLO**, as well with initiatives and approaches working on assessing AE transition, its performance and impacts (i.e. **SoilDiverAgro**, **TAPE – FAO** and **OASIS - ISARA** projects. Synergies with other INFRASERV project (such as **M4C** or **IRISCC**) are also being explored.

The liaison strategy led by consortium members focuses on promoting the development of synergies by each project partner and specially those involved in WP5. The aim is to establish synergies based on their own thematic and geographical relevance and interest for specific RIs, RI groups and consortium members. These synergies are expected to be established mainly with regional or local initiatives. However, since the provision of services has not yet started, it is foreseen that the majority of these type of synergies will take place once the first TA/VA services are provided. This will allow RIs to show the results of their participation in AgroServ project. Information on the liaison processes followed under this approach will be reported in the next version of this deliverable foreseen in M36 (August '26).

Consortium partners, using the living database of potential initiatives to liaise with, should identify potential synergies and collaboration categories and select the most relevant from their own perspective. To support the implementation procedures of these collaborations, three suggestions have been given (Figure 5): i) identify clear reasons for collaboration; ii) identify the specific resources, experiences and knowledge that can be shared for collaboration and iii) set common actions to boost this collaboration. Potential specific collaboration actions are, among others, the invitation to participate in joint events, the preparation of joint proposals to ensure the long-term of AgroServ, the engagement in the task of specific workshops, the engagement and mobilization of stakeholders to participate in the TNA call for proposal or the dissemination of the results of the AgroServ provision of services and tools. Although the collaboration means can be diverse and specific to each initiative, engagement events will be organized with stakeholders once the first TNA services are provided.

Implementation procedures

Some tips for setting up collaborations

1. Identification collaboration goals - links

Why do we need to collaborate?

2. Identification which **specific resources, knowledge, experience** can we obtain and share with them

What can AgroServ bring to them?

What the initiative can bring to AgroServ?

3. **First contact & action plan**

Targeted communication (cared initiatives)

Engagement with a specific WP

Joint events

Joint proposals (linked with WP7)

More after 1st Service provision

Figure 5. Tips for setting collaborations with AgroServ partners related initiatives

AgroServ partners are also encouraged to participate in relevant international and national fora, as well as in specific workshops organized during the project lifetime to disseminate and communicate about the project aims, activities, results and impacts. Information of the most relevant events and initiatives are constantly mapped by the AgroServ communication team and shared in the Newsletters and dedicated social media channels⁴.

Table 6 and 7 show the participation of partners in dissemination and communications activities and the link to the liaison strategy.

⁴ <https://agroserv.eu/agroserv-news>

Table 5. List of dissemination activities performed in AgroServ

	Dissemination Activity Name	WP	What type of dissemination activity?	Who? Target audience	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (1 sentence max)
ALL-READY / ALLERI conference	Participation at a conference on agroecology in Brussels	WP 1	Conferences	Research communities	Inform about AgroServ, TNA opportunities
AI4Life Annual General Assembly	Project meetings	WP 1	Collaborative with EU-funded projects	Research communities	Cooperation between EU projects, advertising TNA
Exchange of experience	Exchange of experience between INFRA-SERV projects towards TNA	WP 1	Collaborative with EU-funded projects	Research communities	Cooperation between EU projects
Interaction with the GRACE-RI	Interactions with the GRACE-RI design phase RI on plant genetic resources	WP 1	Collaborative with EU-funded projects	Research communities	Advertise TNA, discussion about agroecology, interaction between RIs
Interaction with PHENET	Workshop and meetings with the EU project PHENET	WP 1	Collaborative with EU-funded projects	Research communities	Advertise TNA, discussion about agroecology, interaction between RIs
EMPHASIS Training school in Metaponto	Raising awareness about AgroServ	WP 1	Education and training events	Research communities	Advertise TNA, exchange on agroecology
AgroServ conference in Prague	TNA kick-off meeting	WP 1	Conferences	Research communities	Raise awareness about AgroServ, advertise TNA, exchange on agroecology
Agroscope Workshop	Workshop on data management at Agroscope	WP 1	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Raise awareness about AgroServ, advertise TNA, data management in agroecology
Webinar	Agroserv as service provider	WP 1	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Raise awareness about AgroServ, advertise TNA, exchange on agroecology
Webinar	European Research Services on Agroecology: Serving research for the agroecological transition	WP 2	Other scientific collaboration	Research communities	Raise awareness about AgroServ, showcase the catalogue of services and provide guidance on how to exploit it efficiently in a cross-disciplinary context

	Dissemination Activity Name	WP	What type of dissemination activity?	Who? Target audience	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (1 sentence max)
AgroServ conference in Prague	Kick-off meeting of the call	WP 2	Conferences	Research communities	Moderate a working session about "Management and sustainability of agroecosystems, forests and aquaculture" in order to facilitate a participatory discussion and knowledge exchange between researchers and experts on Agroecosystems, Aquaculture and Forestry
Launch of newsletter	Former trainees network (FTN) Newsletter	WP 2	Other	Specific user communities	Presentation of the project and TNA call
final AllReady Conference	Participation as speakers on the final AllReady Conference - 27 September 2023 (https://www.all-ready-project.eu/communication/news-events/news/all-ready-final-conference.html)	WP 5	Conferences	Specific user communities	Advertise of AgroServ project, TNA call, exchange on synergies with the project
6th IMEKOFOODS Conference	Participation as speaker to the 6th IMEKOFOODS Conference - Food on a Global Market - Opportunities and Threats (Dubrovnik, 7-9 Nov. 2022)	WP 6	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
RAFA 2022	Participation as speaker 10th International Symposium on Recent Advances in Food Analysis (Prague, 6-9 Sept. 2022)	WP 6	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
ISOFOOD 2023	Participation as speaker 2ND ISO-FOOD conference "from food source to health" (Portoriz - SI, 24-26 Apr. 2023)	WP 6	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
PRO-GRACE event	Workshop on the Sustainable Management of Plant Genetic Resources - PRO-GRACE project related to the design of the new GRACE-RI (3 Oct. 2023)	WP 6	Collaborative with EU-funded projects	Research communities	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
6th IMEKOFOODS Conference	Participation as speaker to the 7th IMEKOFOODS Conference - Worldwide food trade and consumption quality and risk assessment - (Paris, 25-27 Oct. 2023)	WP 6	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies

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	Dissemination Activity Name	WP	What type of dissemination activity?	Who? Target audience	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (1 sentence max)
Information Day - Horizon Europe - Research Infrastructures	Participation in a information day about Research Infrastructure in Horizon Europe ,On-line, 19.12.2022 (https://www.horizonteeuropa.es/jornada-informativa-sobre-infraestructuras-de-investigacion-en-horizonte-europa)	WP 5	Clustering activities	Research communities	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
Ibergrid Conference	11th Iberian Grid Conference Faro, 10th – 13th October 2022	WP 5	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of the project, its services and the benefits for that research community to access to them
SmartAgrifood Summit	Startup Europe Smart Agrifood Summit (29 September, 2022)	WP 5	Clustering activities	Innovators	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
BeES Conference	Biodiversity and Ecosystem eScience Conference “Threats and challenges to biodiversity and ecosystem conservation from an eScience perspective” (Seville, 22-24 May 2022)	WP 5	Conferences	Research communities	Presentation of AgroServ project to the Biodiversity Research Community
Festival dell'Innovazione Agroalimentare	Festival dell'Innovazione Agroalimentare 9-13 Ottobre 2023	WP 6	Conferences	Industry, business partners	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies and opportunities
European Soil Mission Week	Participation in the Soil Mission Week held in Madrid (21-23 November 2023)	WP 5	Collaborative with EU-funded projects	EU institutions	Exchange and exploring synergies with Soil Mission Projects and initiatives

Table 6. List of communication activities performed in AgroServ

Communication Activity Name	WP	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome
6th IMEKOFOODS Conference	WP 6	Participation as speaker to the 6th IMEKOFOODS Conference - Food on a Global Market - Opportunities and Threats (Dubrovnik, 7-9 Nov. 2022)	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
RAFA2022	WP 6	Participation as speaker 10th International Symposium on Recent Advances in Food Analysis (Prague, 6-9 Sept. 2022)	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
ISOFOOD 2023	WP 6	Participation as speaker 2ND ISO-FOOD conference "from food source to health" (Portoriz - SI, 24-26 Apr. 2023)	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
PRO-GRACE event	WP 6	Workshop on the Sustainable Management of Plant Genetic Resources - PRO-GRACE project related to the design of the new GRACE-RI (3 Oct. 2023)	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
6th IMEKOFOODS Conference	WP 6	Participation as speaker to the 7th IMEKOFOODS Conference - Worldwide food trade and consumption quality and risk assessment - (Paris, 25-27 Oct. 2023)	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
Festival dell'Innovazione Agroalimentare	WP 6	Festival dell'Innovazione Agroalimentare 9-13 Ottobre 2023	Industry, business partners	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies and opportunities
Kick-off meeting of the Agroecology Partnership	WP 5	Participation in the roundtable "Landscape of other initiatives and developing synergies" where AgroServ and other key EU initiatives (i.e. FutureFoodS Partnership, EU Missions-Soil Deal for Europe and Water4All) present potential synergies	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies

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Communication Activity Name	WP	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome
EOSC-Life 4th and final AGM June 2023	WP 9	Presentation of the AgroServ project in the segment on INFRA SERV projects (other ones were c)anSERV and ISIDORe	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project, and Q&A (https://www.eosc-life.eu/news/final-eosc-life-annual-general-meeting/)
6th IMEKOFOODS Conference	WP 6	Participation as speaker to the 6th IMEKOFOODS Conference - Food on a Global Market - Opportunities and Threats (Dubrovnik, 7-9 Nov. 2022)	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
RAFA2022	WP 6	Participation as speaker 10th International Symposium on Recent Advances in Food Analysis (Prague, 6-9 Sept. 2022)	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and exchange on synergies
CROPPINO workshop, Jülich Germany	WP 1	Presentation of AgroServ at the CROPINNO (EU TWINNING project) workshop	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of access opportunities
BarleyMicroBreed workshop, Rabat, Marocco	WP 1	Presentation of AgroServ at theBarleyMicroBreed (EU project) workshop	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of access opportunities
Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry, Pisa, Italy	WP 1	Presentation of AgroServ at the 2024 IEEE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of access opportunities
Metrology for Agriculture and Forestry "	WP 1	Expo at a Horizon Europe event	National authorities	Exhibition	Presentation of the project and access opportunities
Horizont Europa.NRW, Düsseldorf, Germany	WP 1	Workshop about EU projects as success stories	Regional authorities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Presentation of the project and access opportunities
Horizont Europa.NRW, Düsseldorf, Germany	WP 1	Participation with a booth, poster and brochures	Research communities	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, roundtable, group discussion, etc.)	Promotion of fundings available at Euro-Biolmaging including AgroServ (Poster and brochures)

5.1. Joint event organization

In the framework of the AgroServ project, different events for exchange of knowledge, experience and best practices are foreseen to be organized to stimulate discussions among key players, and promote communication and dissemination of project results.

The first event foreseen will be in Bari in October 2024 (tentative agenda in Annex 2). The objective of the two-day workshop will be to establish links and complementarities with relevant EU actors of the AE Community (including other RIs linked with AgroServ services) by sharing knowledge, exchanging experiences and setting a common vision. The following topics have been identified as key to be addressed in the 3 working sessions: i) Exploiting the role of RI in AE Transition; ii) Transdisciplinarity in research and iii) Global standards for assessing and evaluating Agroecological transitions in EU.

Other events for communicating and disseminating the results of the project are also foreseen to be organized by partners participating in WP5 once the first provision of services is finalized. The planning of those events will be included in the next version of this report foreseen in 36 (August 25).

5.2. Stakeholder and Scientific Advisory Board

The database with the relevant initiatives to liaise with was used to select the independent experts representing both the academic community and stakeholders. Thus, the following 4 members, very active and relevant in the EU Agroecology Community and LLs ecosystems, were selected by the AgroServ consortium.

Alexander WEZEL is an associated professor for Agroecology and Landscape Ecology at ISARA-Lyon and the coordinator of the MSc Agroecology. His research deals with management of agroecosystems (biodiversity, drinking water, natural resources) and the analysis of the different interpretations of AE in the world. Wezel has contributed to understanding the complex interactions between agricultural systems and the environment, with a focus on promoting sustainable practices that enhance both productivity and environmental health. His work often emphasizes the importance of integrating ecological principles into agricultural systems to achieve long-term sustainability and resilience. Wezel's research has been influential in shaping discussions and policies related to AE and sustainable agriculture both in Germany and internationally.

Gerald Schwarz is a researcher at Thünen Institute and previously worked as a researcher at Humbolt University of Berlin. His fields of activities deal with European agricultural policies as well as environmental and climate protections & sustainability. He is involved in multiple projects such as AGROECOLOGY Partnership, SHERPA and ALL-READY and has made a variety of publications for those projects.

Giulia Campodonico has over 10 years of work experience in EU policies and projects in the R&D field. Before ENoLL she was leading the EU proposals team of Italian Institute of Technology where she was in charge of coordinating the preparation of collaborative projects proposals in various applied research themes as Robotics & AI, Computation, Smart and nano materials, and Life sciences. She was also leading the training and capacity building activities on EU affairs as well as supporting the Institute alignment and contribution to EU policies and agenda. Her education in

political sciences, European studies, and project management brought her to Brussels where she has worked for different European non-profit organisations as EU project manager in the field of green and digital. Technology and innovation enthusiast, Giulia joined ENoLL in 2022 to work on proposal preparation, project implementation, and advocacy actions.

Torsten Rødel Berg is a senior advisor in the department of Agroecology at Aarhus University. He is known for his work in the field of AE and sustainable agriculture. He has conducted research on topics such as biodiversity, crop diversification, and ecological farming practices. He is involved in relevant AE projects such as AGROECOLOGY Partnership, All-Ready and working groups such as the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) Agroecology Working Group or the Knowledge Network on Sustainable Intensification (FACCE JPI: Agriculture Food Security and Climate Change)

5.3. Next steps

As part of the clustering and liaising with other initiatives strategy the next actions that are needed to take place and that will be further described in next updated version of this D5.3. are the following:

- **Organize, implement and get results of the Workshop “RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES TOWARDS AGROECOLOGY TRANSITION” How to boost our impact by working together? to engage with relevant initiatives (M24).** An important milestone of WP5 is the joint event to foster synergies. While the agenda is currently outlined, effort will be made in the preparation of, and to dynamize, the working session with intent to obtain tangible workshop outputs of use for the Agroecology community (e.g. workshop proceedings, white paper, scientific article).
- **Encourage and implement the liaison strategy led by consortium members.** Effort will be given to support, coordinate and monitor the implementation of synergies between WP5 partners and identified key projects.
- **Prepare the communication and dissemination events whose organization is foreseen under WP5.** Effort will be made to coordinate this preparation and ensure that the relevant WP5 consortium partners and relevant stakeholders are involved in these events.

5.4. Tracking connections

We have implemented a structured approach to tracking connections between AgroServ and the selected initiatives. With this approach, AgroServ reaffirms its commitment to proactive engagement, transparency, and the continual pursuit of synergistic outcomes in advancing sustainable agriculture and AE transitions. Below we list the data sheets completed by partners regarding the different interactions with the selected initiatives. The data sheets include basic information of the initiative and collect details about the nature of collaborations, the progress made, barriers and the opportunities for further alignment.

Name of the initiative	ISIDORE Project
Initiative type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Network <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Audrey Richard Email : audrey.richard@erinha.eu Web : https://isidore-project.eu/
Date of first communication (e.g. email sent)	September 2023

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online / <input type="checkbox"/> Virtual									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Farmer community, association, cooperative <input type="checkbox"/> Private company <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	X	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Description of the synergies	Synergies in TNA Process									
Barriers for collaboration	No funding for mor thorough interaction									
Next steps	Planned regular exchange to address challenges in TNA									
Conclusions	Potential improvement of the TNA process									

Name of the initiative	Bicikl
Initiative type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Network <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Andrew Smith (not a coordinator but a contact) Email : andrew.smith@elixir-europe.org Web : https://bicikl-project.eu/
Date of first communication (e.g. email sent)	September 2023

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online / <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Farmer community, association, cooperative <input type="checkbox"/> Private company <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Description of the synergies	Synergies in TNA Process									
Barriers for collaboration	No funding for mor thorough interactions									
Next steps	Planned regular exchange to address challenges in TNA									
Conclusions	Potential improvements of the TNA process									

Name of the initiative	canSERV
Initiative type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Network <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Jens Habermann Email : coordination.canserv@bbmri-eric.eu jens.habermann@bbmri-eric.eu Web : https://www.canserv.eu/
Date of first communication (e.g. email sent)	September 2023

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online / <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Farmer community, association, cooperative <input type="checkbox"/> Private company <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	x	<input type="checkbox"/>								
Description of the synergies	Synergies in TNA Process									
Barriers for collaboration	No funding for mor thorough interactions									
Next steps	Planned regular exchange to address challenges in TNA									
Conclusions	Potential improvements of the TNA process									

Name of the initiative	AGROECOLOGY Partnership
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Nicolas Tinois and Heather Mckhann Email : n.tinois@fz-juelich.de; heather.mckhann@inrae.fr Web :
Date of first email sent	28.10.23

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time : January 10th at 15:00. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online / <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Private companies <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Description of the synergies	Different synergies have been identified all associated with: 1) articulating the role that Ris can play in AE transitions and 2) disseminate the project results and mobilize stakeholders to participate in the TNA call for applications. AgroServ can feed the Partnership on the lessons learnt on the harmonization and integration of the services provided by RI while the Agroecology Partnership can boost the communication and outreach strategy.									
Barriers for collaboration										
Next steps	Participation in the kick- off meeting and in the liaison event that will take place at M24									
Conclusions	There is a common interest in this collaboration and a synchronization in timings. Further activities are foreseen with this initiative.									

Name of the initiative	VITALISE Project
Contact information of the initiative	Evdokimos Konstantinidis Email : evdokimosk@gmail.com Web : https://vitalise-project.eu/
Date of first email sent	13 November 2023

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time: 24 November 2023 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online / <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Farmers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Private companies <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Description of the synergies	Identify synergies are linked with harmonisation procedures(data management and LLs) , Transnational and Virtual call for applications and training guidelines and actions performed among their research centres.									
Barriers for collaboration	The project is ending soon									
Next steps	Vitalize will share relevant documents on harmonization procedures and a presentation of the project results is foreseen to be given in a consortium meeting									
Conclusions	This collaboration can be very fruitful but it depends on its willingness to collaborate									

Name of the initiative	EULAC ResINFRA & ResINFRA Plus
Initiative type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Network <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Sabina Guaylupo Email: sabina.guaylupo@fecyt.es Web: https://resinfra-eulac.eu/
Date of first communication (e.g. email sent)	27-28 th February, 2023

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time: 27-28th February, 2023, Madrid (Spain) <input type="checkbox"/> Online / <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Onsite									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Farmer community, association, cooperative <input type="checkbox"/> Private company <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Description of the synergies	The project aims to identify the characteristics that would facilitate the sharing of infrastructures on an international level, making them open and available for the use of researchers and generating a coordinated work strategy. The project is ending, but a continuation of the project is planned. AgroServ can contribute to the new project by developing a solid and sustainable framework of cooperation to enhance the regional collaboration on RIs between EU and LAC.									
Barriers for collaboration	Funding for collaboration activities									
Next steps	A continuation with the conversation will start once the new project starts, probably in January 2024.									
Conclusions	Common interest in the establishment of bi-regional collaboration in terms of AE and sustainable agriculture. However, we need to define an action plan to consolidate the collaboration.									

Name of the initiative	Baltic Sea Action Group
Initiative type	<input type="checkbox"/> Project <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Network <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Anne Antman Email : anne.antman@bsag.fi Web : https://www.bsag.fi/sv/kontakt/anne-antman/
Date of first communication (e.g. email sent)	05/02/2024

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online / <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite																		
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Farmer community, association, cooperative <input type="checkbox"/> Private company <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public																		
Work Packages involved	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>WP1</th> <th>WP2</th> <th>WP3</th> <th>WP4</th> <th>WP5</th> <th>WP6</th> <th>WP7</th> <th>WP8</th> <th>WP9</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>						
WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9											
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>											
Description of the synergies	The Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG) has been successful in involving and collaborating with farmers in concrete scientific projects by promoting regenerative agriculture. Here AgroServ could benefit from learning how these collaborations between farmers and scientists have been established, and how farmers can be encouraged to participate in scientific research.																		
Barriers for collaboration	Lack of contact																		
Next steps	Retry to establish contact																		
Conclusions	Good initiative with a lot of possibilities for collaboration for AgroServ.																		

Name of the initiative	AgroHubi
Initiative type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project <input type="checkbox"/> Institution <input type="checkbox"/> Network <input type="checkbox"/> Researchers
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Susanna Lahnamäki Email : susanna.lahnamaki-kivela@luke.fi Web : https://maaseutuverkosto.fi/en/agrihubi/
Date of first communication (e.g. email sent)	11/01/2024

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online / <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Farmer community, association, cooperative <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Private company <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Description of the synergies	AgriHubi is a network gathering Finnish agriculture operators such as farmers, advisors, educators and researchers to collaborate with the aim is to improve farmers' profitability. AgroServ is an interesting actor for the project, as the Finnish/Nordic farmers are interested in inventions and European farming methods as climate change might cause longer growing seasons. They also have hands-on experience of bringing researchers and Farmers together, and struggle with the same questions that is how to close the gap between the farmers and scientists.									
Barriers for collaboration	National level actor									
Next steps	Re-establish contact as soon as AgroSev starts having results coming in.									
Conclusions	Good collaborator									

Funded by
the European Union

Annexes

Annex 1 – Form – tracking liaison, collaboration & networking actions

Name of the initiative	
Contact information of the initiative	Name: Email : Web :
Date of first email sent	

For each contact with the initiative

Meeting information	Data & time : <input type="checkbox"/> Onsite / <input type="checkbox"/> Online									
Main stakeholders involved in the initiative	<input type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input type="checkbox"/> Policy Makers <input type="checkbox"/> Funding bodies <input type="checkbox"/> Farmers <input type="checkbox"/> Private companies <input type="checkbox"/> Press & general public									
Work Packages involved	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	WP9	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Description of the synergies										
Barriers for collaboration										
Next steps										
Conclusions										

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Annex 2 – Potential agenda of the first liaison workshop

Workshop on

“RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES TOWARDS AGROECOLOGY TRANSITION”

How to boost our impact by working together?

2 - 3 October 2024

VENUE - CIHEAM BARI (Via Ceglie, 9, 70010 Valenzano BA, Italy)

BACKGROUND & INTRODUCTION

The EU project AgroServ joints together 12 Research Infrastructures aiming at supporting the transition towards more sustainable systems by providing integrated research services. To ensure a long-lasting impact of the project, we are looking to establish links and complementarities not only among RIs but also with other relevant actors of the Agroecology Community. Sharing knowledge, exchanging experiences allows mutual learning from successes and mistakes, avoids duplication and increases the impact of project results.

Under the framework of this project, we have organized a workshop to discuss 3 major topics of paramount importance within the Agroecology community and RI: i) The role of RI in AE Transition and its collaboration with LLs, ii) Transdisciplinarity in research and iii) the deployment and use of global standards to move towards AE transition.

To discuss these issues, we are organizing the 2 days workshop in the following 3 working sessions.

Working Session 1 - The role of RI in AE Transition

RIs are defined by EC as “*facilities that provide resources and services for research communities to conduct research and foster innovation*”. RI contribute to advancement of excellent science, the mobility of knowledge and researchers and the dissemination and optimization of results in the field of relevance by implementing long-term and FAIR data principles. They can reduce fragmentation of the research and innovation ecosystem, avoid duplication of effort and enhance coordination among researchers to respond to global challenges. RIs within AgroServ address different aspects of the AE and can therefore be important facilities for AE transition as they can support on 1) redesigning of various degrees of agriculture and agri-food, 2) assessing resilience of agroecosystems and 3) dynamics of AE transition. RIs are also complementary to LL, by enabling the transfer of basic science into applications across different scales, they can provide science-based evidence and innovation on key research topics of AE.

The burning questions that will be addressed in this working session are:

- *How can we improve and mainstream the access and use of RI services? How can long-term measurement data be shared and harmonized?*

- *How can we enhance RI collaboration with LLs and other real-based innovation arrangement? How can we share and co-create knowledge and innovation at various scales?*

Working Session 2 - Transdisciplinarity in research

In the ever-evolving landscape of research, the demand for transdisciplinary collaboration among researchers has become increasingly apparent. This is especially relevant in complex disciplines such as agroecology as it simultaneously includes elements from agronomy, ecology, sociology and economics. Researchers, professionals, and experts from various fields need to join forces to address sustainable and resilient agriculture in times of global challenges. Transdisciplinarity is a broad concept encompassing any collaborative effort that brings together expertise, insights, and challenges from various disciplines. Conventional categorization of such collaborative work often revolves around how knowledge and processes from different disciplines are amalgamated and integrated. Transdisciplinarity is essential to address complex problems by integrating the knowledge and methods from multiple disciplines, including diverse viewpoints of the problem. It encourages researchers to confront questions that traditional disciplines do not ask while opening up new areas of research and promotes disciplinary self-awareness about methods and creative practices. However, it also brings important challenges such as the need to codevelop a shared understanding of the domain, issues and key components or the need of involvement of users and non-academic stakeholders in the research and development process.

During this working session we address the following questions:

- *How can EU projects harness the synergy of scientific disciplines to effectively advance the objectives of agroecology and sustainable agriculture?*
- *Which good practices implemented by other EU initiatives can be implemented in AgroServ to foster the advancement in cross-domain research?*

Working Session 3 -Global standards for assessing and evaluating AE transition

The promotion of Agroecology brings the need to evaluate the performance of AE across different scales and contexts. Holistic assessment frameworks are required to determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance of farming systems at different stages of transition toward AE. The results from such assessment frameworks can be used to identify when agroecological practices are effective at meeting multiple locally or globally important outcomes, and when trade-offs arise between development objectives. However, assessment frameworks struggle to balance the trade-off between capturing standardized, globally comparable metrics or capturing metrics that are locally relevant and context-specific (Rosenstock et al., 2017). Establishing these evidence banks provides a valuable resource to catalyse research among agroecology actors to transform food systems to meet production, environmental and social goals in tandem.

During this working session the following questions will be addressed:

- Which are the gaps and limitations of existing monitoring frameworks for assessing Agroecology transition?
- How could RIs (and their specific tools and services) support the implementation of those frameworks?

POTENTIAL AGENDA

2 OCTOBER - DAY 1

11:00-13:00	Welcome lunch/Registration
13:00-13:30	<i>Welcome and Introduction AgroServ project (and how the two topics are addressed)</i> Event organizers Michel Boer (project coordination)
13:30-17:00	Working Session 1: Use of global standards for monitoring AE transition
13:30- 13:50	Agroecology Partnership WP5: Data & Monitoring for AE transition Jose Manuel Avila (LifeWatch ERIC), WP5 Coordinator
13:50 - 14:10	OASIS Indicator system for AE Transition Assessment (backup TAPE, ACT) Alexander Wezel ISARA (tbc)
14:10 - 14:30	SoilDiverAgro (tbc)
14:30- 15:00	Coffee Break
15:00 -16:30	Guided discussion Moderated by Livia Madureira UTAD- Socioeconomics
16:30-17:00	Conclusions of working session

3 OCTOBER - DAY 2

8:30-9:30	Welcome coffee/Registration
9:30-13:00	Working Session 2: Enhancing the role of RI in Agroecology Transition
9:30 - 9:50	Agroecology Partnership. WP7: Expanding the capacities of RIs & LLs Gerald Schwarz (Thuenen Institute), WP coordinator
9:50 - 10:10	Microbes4Climate project (tbc)
10:10 - 10:30	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change risks Project

	<i>(tbc)</i>
10:30-11:00	<i>Coffee Break</i>
11:00 - 12:30	Guided discussion <i>Moderated by Pedro Silva UTAD- Socioeconomics</i>
12:30- 13:00	Conclusions of working session
13:00-15:00	<i>Lunch</i>
15:00-18:00	<i>Working Session 3: Transdisciplinarity in research</i>
15:00-15:15	Agroecology transect Project <i>Bertrand Dumond, INRAE (tbc)</i>
15:15-15:30	AgroMix Project <i>Ulrich Schmutz, Coventry University (tbc)</i>
15:30-15:45	SOLO Soils for Europe Project <i>Helena Guimarães</i>
15:45-16:45	Guided discussion <i>Moderated by Monica Dantas UTAD- Socioeconomics</i>
16:45- 17:15	<i>Coffee Break</i>
17:15-18:00	Conclusions of working session 1 & final conclusions
